

Extended reality in language learning and interpreting: From solutionism to a social constructivist bricolage

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The immersive and interactive technology of extended reality (XR) blurs the lines between the physical and virtual worlds, offering new ways to experience and interact with content. This technology supports a diverse range of applications, from enhancing language acquisition and cultural awareness to improving interpreting skills through realistic simulations. XR is increasingly integrated into language learning, intercultural communication, and interpreter training with the aim of moving beyond mere novelty and unlocking substantial educational potential; the adoption of XR in education emphasizes a transformative learning approach, leveraging the ability of technology to provide immersive multimodal experiences that can lead to better engagement, motivation, and understanding. Despite the optimism surrounding the application of XR to educational settings, challenges related to accessibility, the digital divide, and the potential physical side effects of long-term use remain. The effectiveness of XR in achieving long-term learning gains requires further research. This paper advocates for a balanced understanding of the capabilities of XR, adopting a social constructivist perspective and urging educators to critically assess its impact and potential to enrich the learning experience beyond the initial allure of technological innovation.

Keywords: Extended Reality; Virtual Reality; Augmented Reality; Language Learning; Interpreting; Interpreter Training

1. Introduction

Our everyday actions are inevitably based on a combination of sensory inputs drawing on the material and virtual spheres, and the crossover between the two is so pervasive that it often comes unnoticed. On the one hand, extended reality (XR) simply seems to be amplifying this phenomenon, thanks to the sensory 'affordances' of the technology, but on the other hand, it also seems to generate new potential sets of qualia that would otherwise remain experienced.

Recent advances in mobile technology and the mass utilization of mobile devices, coupled with the constant diffusion of the internet, have contributed to the rapid expansion of XR. Its applications are diverse and are deemed to grow exponentially across different fields. It is sufficient to say that the global

XR market reached 29.26 billion USD in 2022 and is estimated to increase to over 100 billion USD by 2026 (Alsop, 2023).

Despite its diffusion, XR is frequently still treated as a novelty, conceptually and practically; consequently, it is exploited to simply attract the user's initial attention. Nevertheless, XR technologies have enormous (often still underestimated) potential to assist people in activities that go far beyond trivial ones and can include a multitude of complex forms of training and education. The way XR is perceived can also vary immensely; it is, at times, celebrated as a futuristic panacea based on techno-euphoria (or even techno-utopianism), while in some endeavors, it is depicted as an incommensurable threat to a variety of human actions. This polarization often derives from a purely instrumental approach to technology.

This paper aims to inform scholarly activity on the state of the art in the field, offering insights into different approaches adopted in the use of XR and presenting possible future research avenues that are grounded in precise educational approaches. The focal aspect of this reflection is not on the technology per se but rather on how we perceive, conceptualize, and place it within specific theoretical frameworks.

2. Background

2.1. Definitions

In dealing with XR, some definitional issues need to be addressed for clarifying purposes, given its complex, multifaceted, and fluid nature. XR generally refers to different forms of virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), mixed reality (MR), and all the potential technologies that are based on the combination of virtual and real elements. Although these technologies may overlap and share significant aspects, their traditional definitions are based on the following characteristics: VR is a multidimensional immersive space, AR overlays virtual content on real-world content, and MR merges the two perspectives. The notion of XR broadly covers these approaches, as well as possible future ones, in that it is projected toward the acquisition of any potential real, virtual, and hybrid environments.

AR technologies allow for the overlaying of virtual content in physical space in real time (Diegmann et al., 2015). AR applications usually require a handheld device, although the use of a head-mounted display (HMD) may be possible (Fan et al., 2020). AR can offer different experiences. Fundamentally, marker-based AR requires a trigger element that functions as a marker; for instance, a static photo can be scanned via an app, which will subsequently trigger additional content (e.g., animation). Conversely, markerless AR functions without a trigger element. Location-based AR draws on geolocational or

positional data (Cheng & Tsai, 2013), and it is a solution functioning via the sensors of the device, through which any objects can be placed in a given location.

VR completely immerses a user in a synthetic environment; it creates an artificial space, usually without anchoring it in the physical one, which is normally absent from view (Jensen & Konradsen, 2018). The experience is immersive, and the external physical context emerges only sporadically when it is perceived via the interference of elements from outside the virtual setting, for example, the incidental touch of objects (Mills & Brown, 2022), background noise, or sensory stimulation that are typically not part of the actual virtual experience. Generally, user immersion is facilitated by visors or HMDs for stereoscopic vision. These technologies, including motion-tracking controls, contribute to supplying immediate feedback in terms of kinesics, proxemics, and haptics.

MR, by definition, combines physical and virtual environments (Barfield, 2016; Milgram & Kishino, 1994), where interactive objects can respond to users' prompts. XR can be intended as an integration of the different types of realities and virtualities or as an all-encompassing term to refer to all those forms and their potential combinations.

In this articulated and fast-changing framework, we can refer to situations with the prevalence of a real world in which virtual objects are superimposed as AR. When physical objects are integrated into a virtual space, augmented virtuality (AV) can be discussed (Tang et al., 2020). In this view, these situations represent a reality-virtuality continuum (Milgram & Kishino, 1994) in which, at the end of the spectrum, the user experience is characterized by the virtual sphere taking primacy over the physical sphere. This representation aims to transcend dichotomic solutions, and it should not be seen as static but as highly fluid. More specifically, to account for its complexity, we can argue that the reality-virtuality spectrum should be intended as having a multidimensional rather than linear nature in that different technologies may reciprocally feed one another. This contamination makes their distinction particularly unclear and unstable, as the different categories cannot be neatly demarcated.

2.2. Perspectives

XR tools in education can be explored through various theoretical frameworks, notably social constructivism and instrumentalism.¹ Social constructivism emphasizes the collaborative and contextual nature of learning, while instrumentalism focuses on the practical utility and effectiveness of tools. Instrumentalist approaches often lead to positivistic assessments that evaluate technology based on measurable outcomes. In contrast, social constructivist perspectives promote interpretive evaluations, considering the nuanced,

context-dependent impacts of technology on learning (Jonassen, 1991; Vygotsky, 1978).

The expectations placed on technology significantly influence educational practices. When technology is viewed through an instrumental lens, it tends to result in a solutionist narrative.² This perspective simplifies technology's role in merely providing straightforward solutions to educational challenges (Morozov, 2013). Such views often stem from ideological beliefs about what XR technology can achieve, leading to polarized opinions. On the one hand, XR is seen as potentially dangerous, detaching learners from 'reality', while on the other hand, it is hailed as an infallible tool that guarantees exceptional learning outcomes.

This dichotomy reflects broader trends in educational technology discourse in which solutionist approaches dominate. These approaches are based on the assumption that integrating technology will inevitably lead to the attainment of educational objectives across various contexts (Selwyn, 2014). However, shifting away from a purely instrumentalist perspective allows for a more comprehensive understanding of the complexities of XR. Recognizing the role of human agency in shaping technological use highlights the importance of contextual and sociocultural factors in educational practices (Feenberg, 1991).

Educational practices involving technology are inherently situated, with meanings constructed within specific sociocultural contexts. This situational nature means that the effectiveness and impact of XR tools vary based on the individuals and environments involved. Berger and Luckmann's (1966) seminal work on the social construction of reality underscores the importance of these localized contexts. Despite this, the discourse around XR often devolves into debates driven by technophobic fears or overly optimistic expectations, neglecting its potential as a vehicle for constructionist pedagogy (Papert, 1980). Embracing a broader perspective on XR technology, one that goes beyond simplistic instrumentalist views, encourages a more nuanced understanding. It allows educators and researchers to appreciate the potential of XR as a tool for facilitating active and collaborative learning experiences. By focusing on the sociocultural contexts in which XR is deployed, we can better understand its role in enhancing educational outcomes and fostering meaningful learning experiences.

3. The transformative potential of new realities

3.1. XR, language, and literacy

The research literature on XRs is constantly growing, but systematic reviews that offer a detailed discussion of their applications in language-related fields, such as language learning, cross-cultural communication, and interpreting, are

still relatively limited. Indeed, although different language learning endeavors adopt XR technologies, the literature on this topic is still rather partial compared to the diffusion of, and interest in, technology worldwide (Ok et al., 2021).

XR tools have often been developed for business, recreational, or educational purposes, although in the latter case, they seem to be predominately focused on the acquisition of STEM subjects. However, in language learning and in the training of cross-cultural communicators, virtual and augmented technologies can be used with various objectives, such as learning through play, developing soft skills, socializing, improving communicative and pragmatic skills, enhancing diversity awareness, or favoring inclusive communication.

Studies on new literacies, multiliteracies, semiotics, and multimodality have long shown that the very notion of “language and literacy” constantly needs to be reconceptualized (Mills, 2010) according to technological, cultural, and social changes. More specifically, a transformative turn of language learning has long been observed and refers to the common assumption that technologies have a transformative power in the learning process and can dramatically reshape not only the methods, the tools, and the approaches utilized but also its quintessential structure, the relationship between participants, and its outcomes (see Leaver et al., 2021).

In this view, virtual and augmented worlds can be considered a stage in media ecology, where technology has transformative power not only in society but also in the psyche. XR plays a key role in this profound transformation, in that it ineluctably contributes to shaping our individual and social experiences. Indeed, not only does XR allow us to escape our mundane ordinary world and move into other realms, but it also gives us a chance to acquire different forms of experiential knowledge, going beyond the simple activity of imagining ourselves in another situation and experiencing it more directly (although within very specific constraints; see Section 5). These experiences can concern any professional or educational sphere and, consequently, can be extremely useful in training activities. In this respect, rather than focusing exclusively on the unanticipated and unintended consequences of this transformation, critical reflection should be devoted to ways to govern this process and exploit it according to specific pedagogical needs.

3.2. Transmodality and beyond

Transmodality and transmediation can be considerably enhanced by XR technologies, which offer new generative possibilities for acquiring and constructing knowledge, as well as communicating it. XR environments are inherently multimodal, as they are profoundly based on the interaction of different modes, which are not simply juxtaposed but which reciprocally

influence and transform one another. Transmodality plays a key role in XR experiences characterized by the interdependence of semiotic resources and their reciprocal validation to the extent that the distinction between modes somehow transcends (Anesa, 2019). What generates the ultimate value of a certain experience is the interaction of different modes rather than the individual contributions taken in isolation. Moreover, if we consider transmediation to be the process of translating semantic meaning across non-analogous semiotic systems (McCormick, 2011), XR affordances can contribute to the transmediation of semiotic content across varying expression planes or symbolic structures. The translation of information across sign-making systems is never a simple reproduction of content, in that the user needs to engage in processes of adaptation, transformation, and creation (Mills & Brown, 2022).

In XR, we also observe the phenomenon of transensoriality, intended as the coexistence, integration, and mutual enhancement of senses, such as vision, hearing, and tactility, as well as spatial cognition and gestural forms of expression. In this regard, we also experience a tendency to move toward the involvement of the full sensorium in language practice, and even the inclusion of smell and thermo-reception is now possible (Ranasinghe et al., 2016). The reciprocal support of all sensory stimuli contributes not only to the creation of multisensorial practices but also to a holistic approach that constructs the XR experience.

3.3. XR and learning frameworks

The use of XR in language learning, cross-communication, and interpreting training is profoundly based on an interdisciplinary approach, which, by its very nature, lies at the intersection of diverse disciplines, such as information technology engineering, computer programming, experimental pedagogy, linguistics, and psychology. Language-related XR applications draw on different theoretical frameworks. First, they are strongly related to the communicative language teaching (CLT) approach, which can be adopted in both formal and informal communication settings and can be employed with both inductive and deductive teaching methods (Richards, 2006). Within the CLT approach, language skills are not acquired in isolation but through various activities that require interpretation, expression, or negotiation of meaning (Savignon, 2017). Thus, XR technologies can exploit the potential of this approach by favoring the development of complementary skills in immersive experiences.

Second, XR can support the computational thinking approach. Specific attitudes are needed to improve computational thinking skills, such as inner strength and self-confidence in managing complex situations, tenacity in

handling issues and problems, willingness to deal with ambiguity and uncertainty, ability to find flexible solutions, and communication and group management skills (Barr & Stephenson, 2011). XR can provide users with the modes of thinking needed to establish problems while identifying their possible solutions, which represents a valuable foundation for developing a proactive attitude toward solving unprecedented future problems. XR can favor problem-based and collaborative learning (Fortman & Quintana, 2023; Warschauer & Tate, 2018) and can guide users to explore insights from similar issues in different contexts, cultural settings, and domains while searching for solutions. Indeed, the ability to identify, define, and decompose issues through the process of abstraction can be particularly useful in contexts such as interpreting or other communicative activities.

Another group of skills that can be enhanced by XR develops within the 21st century skills framework. This overarching learning framework (Trilling & Fadel, 2012) is based on some key components, such as life and career skills; learning and innovation skills; standards and assessments; information, media, and technology skills; curriculum and instruction; professional development; and learning environment. Other components include critical thinking and problem solving, communication and collaboration, as well as creativity and innovation (Trilling & Fadel, 2012). This is in line with the view that XR education can encourage independent learning, critical thinking, and curiosity as users are generally given room to experiment with flexible and interactive tasks by immersing themselves in different, alternative, and sometimes unexplored contexts. Among the different specific frameworks used to describe so-called 21st century skills, we can cite the model proposed by Binkley et al. (2012), which is based on skills having a global, multicultural focus (Binkley et al., 2012, p. 18). Such skills include:

- Creativity and innovation
- Critical thinking, problem solving, decision making
- Learning to learn and metacognition
- Communication
- Collaboration
- Information literacy (e.g., investigation of sources, evidence, and biases)
- Information and communication technology (ICT) literacy
- Citizenship (global and local)
- Life and career
- Personal and social responsibility

XR in language learning can be fruitfully aligned with the KSAVE 21st century skills framework and can enhance new educational practices, which can allow for the insertion of these skills in curriculum or training design.

3.4. XRALL

Drawing on the well-established concept of CALL (Computer-Assisted Language Learning), the term VR-Assisted Language Learning (VRALL) (see Chan, 2022) has been coined to define VR applications for language learning. A growing amount of research has investigated the affordances of VRALL, and evidence shows that VR can stimulate the development of various skills, such as speaking (Kaplan-Rakowski & Gruber, 2021), listening (Lee, 2019), writing (Pack et al., 2020), and the acquisition of vocabulary (Legault et al., 2019; Madini & Alshaikhi, 2017), cultural awareness, and communicative aptitudes (Yang et al., 2019). XR can also effectively support users with special needs and can enhance motivation, engagement, collaboration, faster learning, and increased memorization processes (Saltan & Arslan, 2017).

Considering the definitional issues illustrated in Section 2, and with the aim of including other technologies beyond the strictly virtual one, I would suggest using the expression XR-Assisted Language Learning (XRALL), which takes into account the complexity, interconnection, and interdependence of presently available approaches based on AR, VR, and MR and their immense potential for further developments and applications. Along the same lines, I would suggest introducing the expression extended learning environments (XLE), drawing on the concept of a virtual learning environment (VLE) in order to potentially refer to those environments where learning processes can draw on different types of reality.

Without adopting a hyper-optimistic perspective on the advantages of XR technologies in language learning and training, and without disregarding the need to contextualize and problematize them (see Section 5), some benefits may be identified. XR no longer requires costly tools for its implementation, and common devices, such as smartphones and tablets, can contribute to leveraging the needs of learners and users across disciplines and can transform learning and training approaches (Hockly, 2019).

While some VLEs are meant to foster learner's autonomy, others focus on interactional skills and collaboration. An immersive and hybrid environment can provide real-time feedback and dynamicity, leading to increased engagement and motivation (Hsu et al., 2022; Parmaxi & Demetriou, 2020). Following Chen et al. (2022), the impact can be in terms of linguistic improvements, content learning, and affective gains. In various educational and training contexts, XR technologies seem to favor 'learning by doing' processes, increase user attention and engagement, and favor motivation and even seem to lead to better decision-making (Radianti et al., 2020).

In traditional educational approaches, the artificiality of settings often represents a barrier to effective language practice, and XR can provide for this

lack of immersive contextualization (Chen et al., 2022). Thus, practice in pseudo-realistic contexts can reduce foreign language anxiety (Dhimolea et al., 2022) and help manage other forms of stress (Chien et al., 2020).

XR technologies facilitate the connection of abstract knowledge to physical input and situate it in a concrete environment (Fan et al., 2022). The orchestration of multisensorial input can have beneficial effects on learning, including language learning (Mills & Friend, 2022; Yu & Smith, 2012), as even abstract mental processes are essentially based on moto-sensory processes (Wilson, 2002). VR and MR technologies are particularly responsive to locomotion, haptics, and kinesics. Moto-sensory and bodily immersion can have multiple benefits in terms of language learning. As Xu and Ke (2014) explained, motor activities can “help to attract attention, stimulate thinking, encode information, concretize concepts, externalize ideas, lower cognitive costs, and offer more modalities or perspectives when learners process cognitive information” (p. 732). The literature also cites the improvement of user attention via bodily engagement, as sensory stimuli can favor the anchoring of key concepts. Indeed, physical engagement and locomotion also enhance the acquisition of content (Mills & Brown, 2022), as well as various personal and interpersonal skills. Research in the area of multisensory perception demonstrates that not only does the involvement of multiple senses enhance cognitive processes, but it also improves efficiency in memorizing and communicating information (Shams & Kim, 2012). In this regard, proprioceptive actions can optimize vocabulary learning (Hald et al., 2016), as well as the development of affective learning and emotion management (Pallavicini et al., 2016), which assumes a key role in interactional processes.

4. XR in language mediation and interpreting

XR can be employed in practicing different types of interpreting, ranging from conference interpreting to community interpreting. In this latter case, one of the advantages of XR, and in particular of VR, is that different professional scenarios (e.g., a police department, a tribunal, a school, a refugees' center, a trade fair, an office, a medical center, or a hospital) can be generated, thus providing a sense of reality, which would otherwise be lacking, even though it should always be kept in mind that the immersive experience is necessarily synthetic (see Section 6). Similarly, via AR, the superimposition of specific virtual objects can help enhance involvement. Following Falbo (2012, pp. 165-168), we can define community interpreting as a “dialog-like” discourse, while conference interpreting is a form of “monologue-like” discourse. The former thus assumes dialogic contours and is generally bidirectional (from, and into, the two languages of the language pair), whereas the latter develops along the lines of monologic communication and is typically unidirectional (into one language).

Community interpreting—also defined as public service interpreting, liaison interpreting, and dialog interpreting, among others—is sometimes identified, in its broad sense, as a form of language mediation; as stressed by Pokorn and Južnič (2020, p. 86), there is some degree of terminological vagueness produced by the interchangeable use of similar terms, such as ‘intercultural mediator’, ‘community interpreter’, and many others. In fact, Community interpreting is interactionally constructed, and segments of speech are typically consecutively translated, following the short consecutive mode. These contexts of communication, however, can also involve cases of whispering, interpreting, and sight-translation practices. The main contexts in which it takes place are healthcare, law, education, welfare, refugee settings, and faith-related settings. Community interpreting allows people who do not speak the societal language to access fundamental services. Despite the delicate role that community interpreters assume in helping guarantee access to basic services, training programs structured according to clear pedagogical frameworks are rare, and hiring practices may belie the urgency of professionalism and qualification. XR, and in particular VR, allow the practice of intercultural mediation dynamics thanks to the simulation of role-play activities in an immersive situation that can replace mere description (Rudvin et al., 2022). It can also be employed in the training of conference interpreters by simulating those processes and, for example, recreating the scenario of a conference hall, and even booths.

Another type of interpreting that is very common, but often insufficiently investigated, is that of travel/escort interpreting, which is typically offered in events such as meetings, trade fairs, and business negotiations. The dynamics according to which it takes place are, to some extent, similar to those of community interpreting, although the purposes are different. Community interpreting is of vital importance because it ensures that people from different linguistic backgrounds can access essential services. Travel interpreting is predominantly business-focused and can have an important impact on businesses and individuals, in that the translation activity can affect decisions, negotiations, and courses of action. The expression “dialog interpreting” can be adopted with a broader semantic meaning and be employed as an umbrella term that can cover both community interpreting and travel/escort interpreting despite the differences in aim, participants involved, and processes. XR can be particularly useful in both cases, in that, by offering immersive experiences, it can help trainees to gain a different understanding of the cultural differences they have to deal with. For instance, through the creation of avatars, users can experience embodiment and learn to manage affect and feelings in a specific milieu, as well as develop supra-linguistic abilities.

4.1. Interpreters' training

Language interpreting represents a complex and dynamic intellectual activity that goes far beyond the interlinguistic transposition of words and involves a vast range of skills. The training of interpreters can be time- and resource-intensive, in that it requires the development of a series of complex abilities, and XR tools can be employed to this end. However, the exigencies of the interpreting community often seem to be ignored, and there seems to be a profound discrepancy between the formal training received by interpreters and the needs of the market (Nai & Hassan, 2022).

The use of VR in the training of interpreters and mediators, although growing, is still sporadic, and the related literature is also currently rather limited (Nai & Hassan, 2022). However, it is possible to capitalize on studies on XR in language acquisition and communication (see Section 3) to apply the most appropriate training protocols and maximize the affordances of the technologies available. Some of the most evident benefits of applying XR to interpreting training are in line with those related to language learning. First, the improvement in language competence enhanced by these technologies represents a key part of an interpreter's training. Second, XR can favor multimodal and multisensory training that facilitates learning-by-doing processes and situated learning, thanks to which users can concretely construct new personas and act in a new simulated real-life environment (Nai & Hassan, 2022). This is particularly relevant in interpreting processes, where, beyond language competence, communicative, pragmatic, and interactional skills need to be developed.

XR tools allow users to immerse themselves in contextualized environments. This approach clearly helps people experience the dynamics emerging in given professional contexts (Nai & Hassan, 2022) but, only sporadically, has the actual training of interpreters been able to apply these research outcomes systematically and exploit them fruitfully. However, some fascinating projects focusing on the use of XR in interpreting training were carried out in the 2010s, and include *Interpreting in Virtual Reality (IVY)* and *Evaluating the Education of Interpreters and their Clients through Virtual Learning Activities (EVIVA)*.³ They focused on the use of VR technology for education and vocational training in interpreting. Some recent case studies also show the positive effects of VR applications in the field (Nai & Hassan, 2022) as well as their use in combination with mobile technology.⁴

Among the benefits of XR in the training of interpreters identified in the literature, we find improvement of interpreting abilities, enhancement of language skills, higher involvement of users, encouragement of critical thinking and self-awareness, better management of stress, increased confidence, and excitement and curiosity (see Chan, 2022). By simulating real-

life scenarios that interpreters may encounter in their professional activities, users have a chance to reduce the artificiality of tasks conducted in class. This approach can lead to more engaging activities and allows rehearsing in a controlled environment, minimizing the risk of potential negative consequences.

4.2. The technological turn in interpreting practice

Interpreting may be seen as being on the verge of a breakthrough due to its rapid technological turn (Fantinuoli, 2018b). The impact of XR technologies and their magnitude could radically transform the profession, as they could profoundly modify not only the training process but also the entire interpreting ecosystem. Fantinuoli (2018b) lists three main areas affected by the technological transformation of the interpreting world: computer-assisted (CAI), remote (RI), and machine interpreting (MI). To these, we could add the role of XR intended as an assisting tool in training, as well as in delivery, or an overarching application that can enhance and contribute to the transformation of CAI, RI, and MI. Following the line of thought introduced in Section 3.4, I would suggest adopting the expression XR-AI (XR-assisted interpreting) to refer to situations in which interpreting processes are assisted by XR technologies.

Computer-assisted interpreting tools can help interpreters in tasks such as the preparation of glossaries or the extraction of information (Fantinuoli, 2018a) but also via advanced NLP tools, which allow, for instance, for automatic speech recognition. These processes can be implemented in both the preparation and delivery phases. Remote interpreting includes a vast series of situations in which the communicative process takes place via ICT (e.g., telephone or, nowadays more commonly, videoconferencing).

MI is also referred to as automatic interpreting, automatic speech translation, or speech-to-speech translation. The spoken text was translated into another language via a computer program. In its basic description, it can be explained as a multiple-phase process, including automatic speech recognition, automatic transcription, machine translation, and speech-to-text synthesis. Although the level of quality achieved in MI is still often insufficient to replace a human interpreter, its accuracy and precision are constantly increasing (Fantinuoli, 2018b); thus, reflection is necessary on the teaching and training practices addressed by future interpreters.

The automatization of the interpreting process may bring with it issues of reification and depersonalization, which may have a considerable impact on specific settings, such as community interpreting, where interactional dynamics play a key role in the outcome of the process. However, it would be anachronistic to try to halt the process *in toto*; rather, its potentialities should be cultivated, while more awareness should be raised of the need to adapt the

use of those tools to the specificities of the type of interpreting, the participants involved, and the issues being discussed. Therefore, particular caution should be taken when dealing with vulnerable people, sensitive topics, or situations where cultural sensitivity is particularly relevant.

Some technology-induced changes in teaching and training in the area of communication and interpreting are momentous, but the constant trend toward the technologization of interpreting cannot be ignored. The relationship between practice and technological innovation has become even more pronounced and can be seen as a tremendous opportunity to fill gaps in specific areas, such as the training of interpreters, which could benefit significantly from the implementation of new practices.

5. Discussion

XR technologies can potentially be used without the physical presence of all participants in the same space. The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly sped up digital changes in education and training processes, with a momentous increase in e-learning, m-learning, and XR-based activities. Thus, it is fundamental to collectively reflect upon whether the implementation of online/remote learning will endure in the post-pandemic scenario and how this transformation will impact the educational and training world, especially in light of advances in XR technologies.

5.1. Impact and potential

XR activities can have significant added value to traditional teaching and training processes, including the following:

- Increased level of motivation, engagement, satisfaction, attention, and enjoyment, in that tasks involving XR technology have been demonstrated to be demanding yet engaging, thereby generating a higher level of interest (see Taskiran, 2019);
- Increased level of accessibility and inclusion by offering the availability of personalized 'just-in-time' input, stimuli, and learning assistance while the user navigates the educational system. This aspect may benefit all users and is particularly in line with the need to support more disadvantaged users or to respond to special needs in an effective way;
- Efficient time management: in particular, in the case of applications and tools that can be used remotely, one can create a personalized learning experience without leaving the element of natural engagement;

- Intensified degree of authenticity in language tasks: XR can offer meaningful, authentic scenarios that can draw the students' interest in practicing the target language in more realistic contexts;
- Enhanced level of performance and results;
- Greater cultural awareness through a more personalized and interactive perception of background, interpersonal, and social contexts (see Yang et al., 2019; Yang & Liao, 2014);
- Higher level of interactivity at different levels (peer and non-peer), promoting teamwork, facilitating exchanges, and stimulating negotiation awareness;
- Improved creativity and reflexivity: AR, for instance, can enhance creativity by offering the opportunity to actively intervene in the augmentation of the reality process, which is stimulating and engaging, and, at the same time, can enhance self-reflexivity about learning processes and objectives and enhance meta-discursive reflections. Users can also be co-authors of content, thus enhancing meaningful collaboration between stakeholders in the educational/training process (see Lee & Park, 2019).

In addition, in acquisitional and training contexts, familiarizing with technologies and XR environments is likely to have an important effect on computer self-efficacy on the part of those involved, thus bringing indirect benefits regarding the development of a broader range of skills (beyond those specifically linguistic ones). Evaluating the improvement of multifaceted types of competence, such as soft skills, is extremely intricate, and a self-reflective approach can help gain a deeper level of awareness of how technologies can enhance them.

5.2. Limitations and concerns

Despite its numerous advantages, the use of XR technologies in language-related learning and training is not free from limitations and raises some concerns. XR can involve a vast range of activities, such as games, narratives, virtual tutors, creative designing, or role plays, but in the educational field, there still seems to be less experimentation and creativity than in apps developed for social and entertainment purposes (Fan et al., 2020). Furthermore, teachers and trainers may not be able to go beyond the apparent rigidity of some apps or exploit their full potential; thus, the products may lack the adaptability and flexibility to suit specific didactic or communicative needs (Fan et al., 2020).

Although the application of XR tools seems to encourage collaborative and active learning, their efficacy in this sense is strongly related to the educational framework within which they are employed, and they are not necessarily absent from traditional problems, such as the decontextualization of materials, ideological biases, and the de-personalization of the learning process. Critical reflection also needs to focus profoundly on the potential development of the dehumanization of teaching practices and the risk for the reification of acquisitional dynamics.

Different justifications for the adoption of XR may be brought up, focusing, for example, on the broad notion of motivation, but such elements are hard to crystalize, especially as XR tools can capture diverse and complementary instantiations of ludic, informative, esthetic, and emotional elements. In addition, there is currently little research on the enduring learning gains of XR applications, with most studies involving short-term pre- and post-study designs (Li et al., 2017), without a focus on long-term outcomes and impacts.

Some may suggest that XR technologies can be intriguing for students at first because of the 'wow' factor and that subsequent interest and motivation may gradually disappear once students have familiarized themselves with the technology. Nevertheless, the constant development of the technology will continue to allow for the implementation of more sophisticated aspects, which are likely to enhance the constant revitalization of the way the tools are perceived. In addition, although becoming more familiar with the technology may minimize the surprise effect, it may also allow users to reduce the attention paid to the instrumental aspect of the activity and to be more focused on content, which in turn would reduce the potential anxiety and stress generated by the adoption of a new tool. In this respect, Dhimolea et al. (2022) noticed that the experimental studies that highlighted a lack of improvement in performance using XR often referred to single exposures to this type of activity, while multiple exposures over time generated better results. Measurability is highly problematic due to the fragmentation of measures and the heterogeneous, sometimes ideologically driven, conception of notions such as results, outcomes, and impact. Measurements are also confounded by the presence of domain-specific approaches that hinder the implementation of consistent evaluative practices. The assessment of the efficacy and efficiency of XR tools is thus obviously complex, and future avenues for research need to move in that direction to reach more reliable results.

Other constraints related to the use of XR include users' reactions, which may include tiredness, motion-sickness, or eye strain. There may also be technical problems with hardware or software systems or the internet connection (Pinto et al., 2021). However, it is reasonable to presume that most of these drawbacks will gradually disappear following technological progress, which is

constantly being implemented to render the use of tools comfortable, trustworthy, and flawless.

Any discussion of XR in education and training should also consider issues related to the digital divide. On the one hand, it may be argued that access to sophisticated XR technologies may not be inclusive and may be available only in elite settings. On the other hand, XR may allow users to overcome some of the limitations that learners and trainees encounter when practicing in real-life settings (e.g., cost of travel), which is particularly important in cross-cultural professional training. Certain technologies, such as AR, can also be acquired with limited investment and are becoming more accessible, so some scholars anticipate that such technologies may actually contribute to bridging, rather than expanding, the digital divide (Fan et al., 2020).

Another important issue is related to surveillance capitalism as a form of tracking mechanism, which is inevitably linked to the use of XR technology for harvesting data, including biometric data—see Giaretta (2022) and O’Hagan et al. (2022) on privacy and security issues. Thus, data concerns need to be urgently addressed and carefully considered when planning the implementation of activities that draw on XR.

6. Conclusion

XR tools in education can be investigated primarily from a social constructivist perspective or from an instrumentalist perspective in terms of conceptualization, production, and usage. Instrumentalist approaches often lead to positivistic evaluations of effectiveness, while social constructivist perspectives seem to encourage more interpretivist evaluations. In this respect, expectations of technology have a big impact on educational practices. Many times, technology is described through an instrumental lens, which may lead to a simplistic account based on a solutionist approach. The underlying (often ideological) expectations of what XR is, and what it can achieve, commonly generate polarized views on its adequacy in educational practices; thus, it is generally considered either as a dangerous tool that can worryingly detach people from ‘reality’ or as an infallible solution that automatically leads to the astounding success of learning outcomes. The fields of application of XR in intercultural and interlinguistic communication are innumerable and range from language acquisition to interpreting practice and training. However, their usage can prove particularly beneficial when adopted within a clear theoretical framework and when self-reflective practices are encouraged.

With its proliferation in terms of tools, usages, contexts, and targets, XR has somehow become deictic, and the related research is expanding considerably as a context-sensitive interdisciplinary field, which is in a constant state of flux. XRs *qua* realities can have a profound impact on how we learn, teach, and

practice. However, it is not suggested here that XR technologies can substitute for other forms of teaching and training but that they represent valuable complementary resources, especially in fields such as intercultural communication.

XR can enhance a deeper understanding of how in situ practice can influence users' perceptions and can encourage them to relate to, and empathize with, their interlocutors in specific time and spatial contexts. Because emotional empathy is one of the components of intercultural sensitivity, the use of XR can favor the development of empathetic practices in intercultural communication, at least under specific circumstances, such as when a certain level of involvement and immersion is generated. In this regard, however, a word for caution is needed. Keeping in mind that XR is often plagued with hyperbole, the equation between immersive spaces and the development of empathetic attitudes should be constantly problematized and should not be treated as automatic. There is often a substantial temptation to strive for the automation of compassion and to idealize XR as a technology of feelings (Nakamura, 2020), failing to acknowledge that such a perception often lies in a critical vacuum. Indeed, there is often a utopian expectation in artificial empathy that tends to disregard the fact that XR is often based on the creation of stigmatized identities and that, simply, 'being immersed' does not equal 'being'.

Learning, training, and literacy practices will continue to undergo a fundamental transformation, exploiting the potential of XR and the evolution of immersive and hybrid social interactions. Given the (relatively) recent use of the technology in these specific training contexts, further investigation is needed, for instance, regarding the effects of eudaemonic factors⁵ on the user's relationship with the technology (and thus on user experience at large).

The debate around XR is often reduced to considerations based on technophobic anxieties or, conversely, on hyperoptimistic anticipation, while it is rarely investigated according to its potential as a form of constructionist pedagogy. Some of the discussions on the use of XR in education and training are necessarily speculative, but it is imperative to reflect on the epistemological values and ethical issues related to the use of such technology. XR is transforming the essence of our relationship to information, to acquisition, and to learning processes and so emerges a renewed sense of urgency that we deepen our understanding of the technology beyond its instrumental aspects.

Pedagogical decisions are often driven by solutionist approaches based on the teleological assumption that the use of technology can automatically lead to objectives being reached in all educational and professional spheres. Moving away from the solutionist and instrumentalist views and embracing a wider constructivist perspective allows us to navigate the complexities of the XR field,

keeping in mind the importance of human agency in constructing specific ontologies around technologies.

Notes

1. For a reflection on constructivism and constructionism in educational contexts, see Wilkinson (2021).
2. Following Morozov (2013), it can be argued that solutionism is fundamentally based on “[r]ecasting all complex social situations either as neatly defined problems with definite, computable solutions or as transparent and self-evident process that can be easily optimized” (p. 5).
3. The two projects are described at: <http://virtual-interpreting.net>
4. See, for example, Chan (2022) who describes the application Virtual Interpreting Practice developed for the practice of interpreting in the English/Chinese language pair.
5. The desire to use XR on the part of the learners or the trainees can depend on a vast series of elements, including eudaemonic factors, such as perceived utility, curiosity, and superior influence (see Ye et al., 2022), but the investigation of their impact in terms of user experience still appears to be in an embryonic phase.

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References

- Alsop, T. (2023). *XR market size worldwide 2021-2026*. Statista. www.statista.com/statistics/591181/global-augmented-virtual-reality-market-size
- Anesa, P. (2020). How to do things with modes: Transmodality in slides. *Lingue e Linguaggi*, 33, 7-23. <https://doi.org/10.1285/i22390359v33p7>
- Barfield, W. (Ed.). (2016). *Fundamentals of wearable computers and augmented reality* (2nd ed.). CRC Press.
- Barr, V., & Stephenson, C. (2011). Bringing computational thinking to K-12: What is involved and what is the role of the computer science education community? *ACM Inroads*, 2(1), 48-54. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1929887.1929905>
- Berger, P. L., & Luckmann, T. (1966). *The social construction of reality: A treatise in the sociology of knowledge*. Anchor Books.
- Binkley, M., Erstad, O., Herman, J., Raizen, S., Ripley, M., Miller-Ricci, M., & Rumble, M. (2012). Defining twenty-first century skills. In P. Griffin, B. McGaw & E. Care (Eds.), *Assessment and teaching of 21st century skills* (pp. 17-66). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-2324-5_2
- Chan, V. (2022). Using a virtual reality mobile application for interpreting learning: listening to the students' voice. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 32(6), 2438-2451. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2022.2147958>
- Chen, B., Wang, Y., & Wang, L. (2022). The effects of virtual reality-assisted language learning: A meta-analysis. *Sustainability*, 14(6), 3147. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14063147>

- Cheng, K.-H., & Tsai, C.-C. (2013). Affordances of augmented reality in science learning: Suggestions for future research. *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, 22(4), 449-462. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10956-012-9405-9>
- Chien, S.-Y., Hwang, G.-J., & Jong, M. S.-Y. (2020). Effects of peer assessment within the context of spherical video-based virtual reality on EFL students' English-speaking performance and learning perceptions. *Computers & Education*, 146, 103751. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2019.103751>
- Dhimolea, T. K., Kaplan-Rakowski, R., & Lin, L. (2022). A systematic review of research on high-immersion virtual reality for language learning. *TechTrends*, 66(5), 810-824. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11528-022-00717-w>
- Diegmann, P., Schmidt-Kraepelin, M., Eynden, S., & Basten, D. (2015). Benefits of augmented reality in educational environments: A systematic literature review. *Wirtschaftsinformatik Proceedings 2015*. <https://aisel.aisnet.org/wi2015/103>
- Falbo, C. (2012). CorIT (Italian television interpreting corpus): Classification criteria. In F. Straniero Sergio & C. Falbo (Eds.), *Breaking ground in corpus-based interpreting studies* (pp. 157-185). Peter Lang.
- Fan, M., Antle, A. N., & Warren, J. L. (2020). Augmented reality for early language learning: A systematic review of augmented reality application design, instructional strategies, and evaluation outcomes. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 58(6), 1059-1100. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0735633120927489>
- Fantinuoli, C. (2018a). Computer-assisted interpreting: Challenges and future perspectives. In I. Durán & G. Corpas Pastor (Eds.), *Trends in e-tools and resources for translators and interpreters* (pp. 153-174). Brill.
- Fantinuoli, C. (2018b). Interpreting and technology: The upcoming technological turn. In C. Fantinuoli (Ed.), *Interpreting and technology* (pp. 1-12). Language Science Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1493289>
- Feenberg, A. (1991). *Critical theory of technology*. Oxford University Press.

- Fortman, J., & Quintana, R. (2023). Fostering collaborative and embodied learning with extended reality: Special issue introduction. *International Journal of Computer-Supported Collaborative Learning*, 18, 145-152. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11412-023-09404-1>
- Giaretta, A. (2022). *Security and privacy in virtual reality: A literature survey*. arXiv, 20 May 2022. <http://arxiv.org/abs/2205.00208>
- Hald, L. A., De Nooijer, J., Van Gog, T., & Bekkering, H. (2016). Optimizing word learning via links to perceptual and motoric experience. *Educational Psychology Review*, 28(3), 495-522. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-015-9334-2>
- Hockly, N. (2019). Augmented reality. *ELT Journal*, 73(3), 328-334. <https://doi.org/10.1093/elt/ccz020>
- Hsu, C.-C., Chen, Y.-L., Lin, C.-Y., & Lien, W. (2022). Cognitive development, self-efficacy, and wearable technology use in a virtual reality language learning environment: A structural equation modeling analysis. *Current Psychology*, 41(3), 1618-1632. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-021-02252-y>
- Jensen, L., & Konradsen, F. (2018). A review of the use of virtual reality head-mounted displays in education and training. *Education and Information Technologies*, 23(4), 1515-1529. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-017-9676-0>
- Jonassen, D. H. (1991). Evaluating constructivist learning. *Educational Technology*, 31(9), 28-33.
- Kaplan-Rakowski, R., & Gruber, A. (2021). One-on-one foreign language speaking practice in high-immersion virtual reality. In Y.-J. Lan & S. Grant (Eds.), *Contextual language learning* (pp. 187-202). Springer Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-3416-1_9
- Leaver, B. L., Davidson, D., & Campbell, C. (Eds.) (2021). *Transformative language learning and teaching*. Cambridge University Press.
- Lee, A. (2019). Using virtual reality to test academic listening proficiency. *Korean Journal of English Language and Linguistics*, 19(4), 688-712. <https://doi.org/10.15738/kjell.19.4.201912.688>

- Lee, S. M., & Park, M. (2019). Reconceptualization of the context in language learning with a location-based AR app. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 33(8), 1-24.
- Legault, J., Zhao, J., Chi, Y.-A., Chen, W., Klippel, A., & Li, P. (2019). Immersive virtual reality as an effective tool for second language vocabulary learning. *Languages*, 4(1), 13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/languages4010013>
- Li, J., Van Der Spek, E. D., Feijs, L., Wang, F., & Hu, J. (2017). Augmented reality games for learning: A literature review. In N. Streitz & P. Markopoulos (Eds.), *Distributed, ambient and pervasive interactions* (Vol. 10291, pp. 612-626). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-58697-7_46
- Madini, A., & Alshaihi, D. (2017). Virtual reality for teaching ESP vocabulary: A myth or a possibility. *International Journal of English Language Education*, 5(2), 111. <https://doi.org/10.5296/ijele.v5i2.11993>
- McCormick, J. (2011). Transmediation in the language arts classroom: Creating contexts for analysis and ambiguity. *Journal of Adolescent & Adult Literacy*, 54(8), 579-587. <https://doi.org/10.1598/JAAL.54.8.3>
- Milgram, P., & Kishino, F. (1994). A taxonomy of mixed reality visual displays. *IEICE Transactions on Information and Systems*, 77, 1321-1329.
- Mills, K. A. (2010). A review of the "Digital Turn" in the new literacy studies. *Review of Educational Research*, 80(2), 246-271. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654310364401>
- Mills, K. A., & Brown, A. (2022). Immersive virtual reality (VR) for digital media making: Transmediation is key. *Learning, Media and Technology*, 47(2), 179-200. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17439884.2021.1952428>
- Mills, K. A., & Friend, L. (2022). Analyzing children's virtual reality: Research Vignette 14. In F. Serafini (Ed.), *Beyond the visual: An introduction to researching multimodal phenomena* (pp. 184-188). Teachers College Press.
- Morozov, E. (2013). *To save everything, click here: Technology, solutionism and the urge to fix problems that don't exist*. Public Affairs.

- Nai, R., & Hassan, H. (2022). Multi-modal simultaneous interpreting teaching: Based on situated learning in virtual reality. In Y. Pei, J.-W. Chang & J. C. Hung (Eds.), *Innovative computing* (Vol. 935, pp. 494-501). Springer Nature. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-4132-0_61
- Nakamura, L. (2020). Feeling good about feeling bad: Virtuous virtual reality and the automation of racial empathy. *Journal of Visual Culture*, 19(1), 47-64. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1470412920906259>
- O'Hagan, J., Saeghe, P., Gugenheimer, J., Medeiros, D., Marky, K., Khamis, M., & McGill, M. (2022). Privacy-enhancing technology and everyday augmented reality: Understanding bystanders' varying needs for awareness and consent. *Proceedings of the ACM Interactive, Mobile Wearable Ubiquitous Technologies*, 6(4), 177. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3569501>
- Ok, M. W., Haggerty, N., & Whaley, A. (2021). Effects of video modeling using an augmented reality iPad application on hedonics performance of students who struggle with reading. *Reading & Writing Quarterly*, 37(2), 101-116. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10573569.2020.1723152>
- Pack, A., Barrett, A., Liang, H.-N., & Monteiro, D. V. (2020). University EAP students' perceptions of using a prototype virtual reality learning environment to learn writing structure. *International Journal of Computer-Assisted Language Learning and Teaching*, 10(1), 27-46. <https://doi.org/10.4018/IJCALLT.2020010103>
- Pallavicini, F., Argenton, L., Toniazzi, N., Aceti, L., & Mantovani, F. (2016). Virtual reality applications for stress management training in the military. *Aerospace Medicine and Human Performance*, 87(12), 1021-1030. <https://doi.org/10.3357/AMHP.4596.2016>
- Papert, S. (1980). *Mindstorms: Children, computers, and powerful ideas*. Basic Books.
- Parmaxi, A., & Demetriou, A. A. (2020). Augmented reality in language learning: A state-of-the-art review of 2014-2019. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 36(6), 861-875. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcal.12486>
- Pinto, R. D., Peixoto, B., Melo, M., Cabral, L., & Bessa, M. (2021). Foreign language learning gamification using virtual reality—A systematic review of empirical research. *Education Sciences*, 11(5), 222. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11050222>

- Pokorn, N., & Južnič, T. M. (2020). Community interpreters versus intercultural mediators. Is it really all about ethics? *Translation and Interpreting Studies, 15*, 80-107. <https://doi.org/10.1075/tis.20027.koc>
- Radianti, J., Majchrzak, T. A., Fromm, J., & Wohlgenannt, I. (2020). A systematic review of immersive virtual reality applications for higher education: Design elements, lessons learned, and research agenda. *Computers & Education, 147*, 103778. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2019.103778>
- Ranasinghe, N., Jain, P., Tolley, D., Karwita, S., Yilei, S., & Do, E. Y.-L. (2016). AmbioTherm: Simulating ambient temperatures and wind conditions in VR environments. *Proceedings of the 29th Annual Symposium on User Interface Software and Technology*, 85-86. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2984751.2985712>
- Richards, J. (2006). *Communicative language teaching today*. Cambridge University Press.
- Rudvin, M., Di Gennaro, E., & Di Rosa, R. T. (2022). Training language mediators and interpreters through embodied cognition, immersion learning and virtual reality: Didactic, organizational, and cost benefits. Introduction to the special section. *Italian Journal of Sociology of Education, 14*(3), 131-152.
- Saltan, F., & Arslan, Ö. (2016). The use of augmented reality in formal education: A scoring review. *EURASIA Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education, 13*(2), 503-520. <https://doi.org/10.12973/eurasia.2017.00628a>
- Savignon, S. J. (2017). Communicative competence. In J. I. Liantas (Ed.), *The TESOL encyclopedia of English language teaching* (1st ed., pp. 1-7). Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118784235.eelt0047>
- Selwyn, N. (2014). *Distusting educational technology: Critical questions for changing times*. Routledge.
- Shams, L., & Kim, R. (2012). Cross-modal facilitation of unisensory learning. In B. E. Stein (Ed.), *The new handbook of multisensory processing* (pp. 475-482). MIT Press. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/8466.003.0042>

- Tang, Y. M., Au, K. M., Lau, H. C. W., Ho, G. T. S., & Wu, C. H. (2020). Evaluating the effectiveness of learning design with mixed reality (MR) in higher education. *Virtual Reality*, 24(4), 797-807. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10055-020-00427-9>
- Taskiran, A. (2019). The effect of augmented reality games on English as foreign language motivation. *E-Learning and Digital Media*, 16(2), 122-135. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2042753018817541>
- Trilling, B., & Fadel, C. (2012). Tactics for success. *RSA Journal*, 158(5550), 10-15. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26204110>
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in society: The development of higher psychological processes*. Harvard University Press.
- Warschauer, M., & Tate, T. (2018). Digital divides and social inclusion. In K. A. Mills, A. Stornaouiolo, A. Smith & J. Z. Pandya (Eds.), *Handbook of writing, literacies, and education in digital cultures* (pp. 63-75). Routledge.
- Wilkinson, P. (2021). *Purposing digital media for education: Critically exploring values and expectations in applying digital media for children's learning and development* [PhD thesis]. Bournemouth University.
- Wilson, M. (2002). Six views of embodied cognition. *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review*, 9(4), 625-636. <https://doi.org/10.3758/BF03196322>
- Xu, X., & Ke, F. (2014). From psychomotor to 'motorpsycho': Learning through gestures with body sensory technologies. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 62(6), 711-741. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-014-9351-8>
- Yang, M., & Liao, W. (2014). Computer-assisted culture learning in an online augmented reality environment based on free-hand gesture interaction. *IEEE Transactions on Learning Technologies*, 7(2), 107-117. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TLT.2014.2307297>
- Yang, Y., Wu, S., Wang, D., Huang, Y., & Cai, S. (2019). Effects of learning activities based on augmented reality on students' understanding and expression in an English class. In M. Chang, H. J. So, L. H. Wong, F. Y. Yu & J. L. Shih (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 27th International Conference on Computers in Education* (pp. 685-691). Asia-Pacific Society for Computers in Education.

- Ye, Q., Zhou, R., Anwar, M. A., Siddiquei, A. N., Hussain, S., & Asmi, F. (2022). Virtual reality-based learning through the lens of eudaemonic factors: Reflective thinking as a game changer. *Thinking Skills and Creativity, 45*, 101103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2022.101103>
- Yu, C., & Smith, L. B. (2012). Embodied attention and word learning by toddlers. *Cognition, 125*(2), 244-262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2012.06.016>